

Full Length Research Paper

Chemical Composition of Two Varieties of *Arachis hypogaea*

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In Northern Nigeria, *Arachis hypogaea* (Groundnut) is mostly consumed as oil, confectionaries, groundnut paste etc. with little or no consideration given to the groundnut species or their chemical composition because most consumers rely on availability rather than quality. In the present study, the groundnut varieties Kampala and Munchi which are mostly used for oil extraction, consumption, and production of confectionaries in Yola were analyzed for their proximate contents, qualitative phytochemical screening, heavy metals, anti-nutrients, and antioxidants vitamins (A and E). Tannins, glycoside, steroids, and phenols were absent in both groundnut varieties. Kampala had the highest amounts of moisture (5.51%), crude fibre (16.75%), and crude lipid (48.80%), while Munchi contains saponins, flavonoids and alkaloids. Kampala contains flavonoids and alkaloids. Munchi variety had the highest amounts of ash content (1.94%), crude protein (33.94%), and carbohydrate (6.72%), respectively. High levels of

Ca and Fe were detected in Kampala, while Pb, Cd, and P were not detected in both varieties. Oxalate and cyanogenic glycoside were higher in Kampala and phytate were higher in Munchi. Vitamin E was present more in Munchi than in Kampala, while both groundnut varieties did not contain vitamin A. This study reveals the presence of considerably high amounts of lipids, moisture, proteins and fibre in both samples which makes the seeds an excellent economic source for edible oil production. The presence of Ca, Fe and vitamin A in both samples makes them suitable in human feeds. The study therefore provides an insight into the chemical and nutritional composition of the two (Munchi and Kampala) groundnut varieties.

Keywords: *Arachis hypogaea*, nutrients, antioxidants vitamins anti-nutrient, mineral elements

INTRODUCTION

Legumes are edible seeds enclosed in pods belonging to the family *fabaceae* (or *leguminosae*). A legume fruit is a simple dry fruit that develops from a simple carpel and usually dehisces (opens along a seam) on two sides. Legumes are grown agriculturally, primarily for their grain seed called pulse, for livestock forage and silage, and as soil enhancing green manure. Well known legumes include alfalfa, cover, peas, beans, peanuts, chicken peas, lentils, lupin bean, mesquite, carob, soybeans and tamarind (Burnham and Johnson, 2004).

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*), or peanut is a species in the legume family *Fabaceae* native to South America, Mexico and Central America (Dillehay and Tom, 2007). It is a legume which is widely grown as a food crop. It is also an herbaceous plant of which there are different

varieties such as Boro light, Boro Red, Mokwa, Kampala, Guta and Ela (Anyasor *et al.*, 2009). Peanut is an important source of edible oil for millions of people living in the tropics. It is among the oldest oil crops in Nigeria and is mostly consumed as Snack, after roasting (Jambunathan *et al.*, 1993). Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) is an important oil seed(s) ranking 13th globally (Ganesh *et al.*, 2015) with significant economic importance due to its use directly in food, animal feeding, confectionery industries and in the production of biodiesel (Tasso *et al.*, 2004), and one of most important leguminous crops in north eastern Nigeria as well as in many parts of the world. It is an important cash crop for farmers of the region and plays an important agronomical role in the traditional farming system as a

source of nitrogen (N fixer) for cereals (Shiyam, 2010). Peanuts are used for popular confections such as ground nutcake (“kulikuli”), salted-peanuts, peanut-butter (sandwiches, candy bars and cup), peanut-brittle, stir-frys, beer-nuts and shelled-nuts (plain/roasted).

Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea*) is a cash crop that is normally cultivated during the rainy season in the semi-arid regions of the world (Junjittakarna *et al.*, 2013). Its growing areas are found in the tropical and subtropical climate zones of the world (where heat systems are suitable for both vegetative and fruit growth) (Intsar *et al.*, 2015), where its seeds are used either directly for human consumption or exploitation (Caliskan *et al.*, 2008). It has contributed extremely to the development of the Nigerian economy through the sales of seeds, cakes, oil and haulms. A part from being consumed raw, edible groundnuts are processed into many local foods or included as an ingredient in a wide range of other products which includes groundnut paste which is fried to obtain groundnut cake (kuli kuli), salted groundnut (gyada mai gishiri), a gruel or porridge made with millet and groundnut (kunun gyada), groundnut candy (kantun gyada) and groundnut soup (miyar gyada). The shells are used for fuel by some local oil factories or they are sometimes spread on the field as a soil amendment. They could also be used as bulk in livestock rations or in making chipboard for use in joinery (Mukhtar, 2009). Recently, the use of groundnut meal is becoming more recognized not only as a dietary supplement for children on protein poor cereals-based diets but also as effective treatment for children with protein related malnutrition. Healthy population promotes development of the people through the relation between food, nutrition and health which needs to be reinforced in order to satisfy the needs of the increasing population.

Groundnut provides an inexpensive source of high quality dietary protein and oil. The vast food preparations incorporating groundnut to improve the protein level has helped in no small way in reducing malnutrition in the developing countries (Asibuo *et al.*, 2008). Groundnut protein is increasingly becoming important as food and feed sources, especially in developing countries where protein from animal sources are not within the means of the majority of the populace. The seed has several uses as whole seed or processed to make peanut butter, oil soups, stews and other products. The cake has several uses in feed and infant food formulations. Groundnut provides considerable amounts of mineral elements to supplement the dietary requirements of humans and farm animals (Asibuo *et al.*, 2008). It is the 4th major oilseeds crop of the world next to soybean, rapeseed and cotton. In 2015, it contributed 8.7% of the total oil seeds production (45 million ton) in the world (Anonymous, 2015). Peanut is an important oilseed crop for vegetable oil production (Arioglu, 2014). About 2/3 of total peanut production is crushed for oil and the remaining one-third is used in confectionery products in the world (Dwivedi *et*

al., 1993).

Vegetable oil is always at a higher price per ton than the cake, this is because the demand for oil is often higher than the cake. Nut and seed oils are receiving growing interest due to their high concentration of bioactive lipid components which have shown various health benefits. Fats and oils, and their several lipid components can extensively be used in the food and also in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, biodiesel paints and other.

Oils from most edible oils seeds are used in the food industry, though there is growing emphasis on industrial utilization as feedstock for several industries with about 80% of the world production of vegetable oils for human consumption. The remaining 20% utilization is between animal and chemical industries. The ability of a particular oilseed fit into the growing industries depends on its utilization potential, rate of production, availability and ease of the processing technology. The aim of this study was to investigate the chemical composition of two varieties of groundnuts (Kampala and Munchi) grown in Yola, Adamawa state.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Two groundnut varieties commonly used for production of groundnut oil in Yola were used for this research study, namely-Kampala and Munchi groundnut variety.

Equipment and apparatus

Weighing balance, muffle furnace, dessicator, Kjeldahl flask, soxhlet apparatus, conical flask, Whatman no. 1 filter paper, magnetic stirrer, oven, heater, volumetric flask, test tubes, water bath, crucibles, beakers, analytical balance, volumetric flask, atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS), HPLC.

Methodology

Collection of samples

The two varieties of groundnut (Kampala and Munchi) were obtained from groundnut local farmers in Yola metropolis and were identified by the plant science department of the University.

Sample preparation

Each of the groundnut variety was carefully sorted to remove stones. It was dehusked and blended traditionally.

Procedures for proximate analysis

Determination of moisture content

The standard method of AOAC, (2000) was used to determine the moisture content of the samples. Briefly, clean crucibles with lids were labeled and dried in an oven at 100°C for 30 min; it was allowed to cool in a suitable desiccator containing CaO as a desiccant and weigh to a constant weight. The sample was grinded to fine powder and mixed to obtain a homogenous sample of large surface area. An analytical balance (Mettler Toedo AB 204) was used to obtain the weight of the crucibles with the lids. In each of the crucibles, 2.0 g was placed in it and dried in the oven at 100°C for 17 h. The samples were removed from the oven and the lids were replaced, the sample are then transferred to a desiccator containing CaO as desiccant to room temperature (28± 1°C) and weighed. The process was continued until a constant weight is obtained. A triplicate determination was carried out on each sample.

Calculation

The percentage moisture content was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Moisture (\%)} = \frac{t-u}{S} \times 100$$

Where

S = Weight of sample for analysis
t = Weight of sample + crucible before drying
u = Weight of sample + crucible after drying
t - u = Loss of weight or moisture content

Total ash: The ash content was determined by method of AOAC, (2000).

Procedure

Porcelain crucibles with lids was ignited for 5 min in a muffle furnace (M-525) at 550°C, cooled in a *desiccators* and weighed. Two grams of each sample was separately weighed into the appropriately labeled crucible and weighed again. Crucible and content was ignited in the muffle furnace (Model M- 525) at 550°C for 18 h to light grey ash. Thereafter, they were removed and placed immediately in a *desiccators* to cool and weighed.

Calculation

The difference in weight or loss in weight of the crucible and sample before ashing will give the organic matter content of each diet, while the difference between the

weight of the crucibles alone and crucible and ash and gives the weight of the ash of each sample. Values for ash were calculated and expressed in percentages as:

$$\text{Ash (\%)} = \frac{X-Y}{Z}$$

Where

X = Weight of crucible and content after drying
Y = Weight of empty crucible
X-Y = Weight of ash
Z = Weight of sample

Crude protein

Crude protein was estimated using micro-Kjeldahl method. The method involves digestion and titration. About 0.2 g of each sample was weighed into a 100 ml Kjeldahl digestion flask. Two and half grams of (2.5 g) of anhydrous sodium sulphate, 0.5 copper sulphate (catalyst) and 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added. The flask was placed on a heater and gently initially, until the solution turns black. After this, heat was increased to obtain a clear solution, cooled, washed and transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask and rinsed with distilled water to mark.

Fat

This was determined using the official method of AOAC, (2000). Two grams of each sample was extracted with petroleum ether (40-60°C) using Soxhlet extractor. The extract was evaporated at 70°C to remove any remaining solvent present. The apparatus was reweighed and percentage fat calculated as follows:
Percentage crude fat = Weight of oil/weight of sample × 100.

Carbohydrate

The carbohydrate content of the samples was determined as the difference obtained after subtracting the values of moisture content, ash, organic protein, and lipid content from the total dry matter.
Carbohydrate = 100 – (moisture content + ash + protein + lipid content)

Procedure for anti-nutrient analysis

Oxalate

Seventy five ml of 1.5 N H₂SO₄ were added to 1g of sample and stirred intermittently with a magnetic stirrer for about 1 h and filtered using Whatman no. 1 filter paper. 25 ml of filtrate were titrated hot (80-90°C) against

0.1 N KMnO_4 solution to the point when a faint pink color appears and persists for at least 30 seconds (AOAC, 2007).

Phytate

Phytic acid was determined by the procedure of Lucas and Markakas (1975). Two g of the sample was weighed into a 250 ml conical flask. 100ml of 2% concentrated HCl was used to soak sample for 3 hours and then filtered with a Whatman No. 1 filter paper. 50 cm^3 of the filtrate and 10 cm^3 of distilled water are added in each case to give proper acidity. 10 ml of 0.3% ammonium thiocyanate solution was added into the solution as indicated and titrated with standard Iron II Chloride solution containing 0.00195g Iron/ml, end point observed to be yellow which persisted for 5 min.

The % phytic acid was calculated, thus:

$$\% \text{ Phytic acid} = y \times 1.19 \times 100$$

Where

$$Y = \text{Titre value} \times 0.00195 \text{ g}$$

Cyanogenic glycoside

The alkaline picrate method of Oke, (1969) was adopted. 5.0 g of the samples was weighed and dissolved in 50 ml distilled water in corked conical flasks. The mixtures were allowed to stay overnight and then filtered. The extracts (filtrates) were collected and labeled A and B. Different concentration of hydrogen cyanic acid (HCN) was prepared containing 0.02 to 0.10 mg/mL cyanide. The absorbance of each was taken in a spectrophotometer at 490 nm and the cyanide standard curve was plotted. 1 mL of each sample filtrate and standard cyanide solution will be measured in to test tubes respectively and 4 ml of alkaline picrate solution will be added to each and incubated in a water bath for 15 min. After color development (reddish brown), the absorbance of each content in the test tubes was taken in a spectrophotometer at 490 nm against a blank containing only 1 ml distilled water and 4 ml alkaline picrate solution (1g of picrate and 5g of sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) was dissolved in a warm water in 200 mL flasks and made up to 200 ml with distilled water). The cyanide content for each sample was extrapolated from the cyanide curve.

Determination of heavy metals

The method described by AOAC, (1980) was adopted. Calcium, lead, cadmium, iron and phosphorus were analyzed from the triple acid digestion (wet digestion method). Exactly 1 g of the samples were weighed each

into a 150 mL beaker, and 10 mL of conc. HNO_3 was added to each sample in the beaker and allowed to soak thoroughly. 3 mL of 60% HClO_4 was added and the mixtures were heated slowly at first until frothing ceases. Heating continued until HNO_3 evaporated; the heating was stopped as charring occurs. 10 mL conc HNO_3 was added and heating continued until white fumes are observed. The digests was allowed to cool and 10 mL conc. HCl was added and transferred to 50 mL volumetric flask. The volume of the solutions was made up to the mark with distilled water, and then transferred to a bigger flask. The solutions were further diluted to 100 mL with distilled water. Calcium, phosphorus and iron were measured using atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Qualitative phytochemical screening

The qualitative phytochemical screening of the samples was carried out as described by Nweze *et al.* (2004). The groundnut samples were screened for alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, glycoside, tannins, phenols and steroids.

Test for steroids

1 g of each sample, equal volume of chloroform and 3 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid was added. Formation of brown ring indicates the presence of steroids.

Test for saponins

1 g of each sample, 5-10 ml distilled water was added and shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 min. Formation of 1 cm layer of foam indicates the presence of saponins.

Test for flavonoids

2 g of each sample, 1 ml of aqueous NaOH solution was added and observed for the formation of yellow-orange coloration. 2 g of each sample was treated with 4 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid and observed the formation of orange colour.

Test for glycosides

2 g of each samples, 1 ml glacial acetic acid and 5% ferric chloride added. 3 drops of Mayer's reagent was added. Presence of green colour or white precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides.

Test for tannins

1 g of each sample, 2 ml of 50% ferric chloride was added. Formation of dark blue or green-black colour indicates the presence of tannins.

Test for alkaloids

Few drops of picric acid solution were added to 5 g of each sample. Formation of orange colouration indicates the presence of alkaloids.

Test for phenol

2 ml of the sample was added to 2 ml of ferric chloride (FeCl_3), deep bluish green solution is formed with presence of phenols.

Determination of vitamins A and E

The method of HPLC (High Performance Liquid Chromatography) was used for the determination of vitamins A and E, briefly, analysis will be performed by injecting 20 μL of carefully prepared sample into a bulk scientific (USA) BLC 10/11-model HPLC equipped with UV-325 nm and UV 254 nm detectors for fat soluble vitamins. AC18, 4.6 \times 150 mm, column and a mobile phase of 95:5 (methanol: water) were used at a flow rate of 1.00 mL/min and an ambient operating temperature. A 1.0 mg of mixed standards was analyzed in a similar manner for identification. Peak identification was conducted by comparing the retention times of authentic standards and those obtained from the samples. Concentrations were calculated using a four way calibration curve (Sarkiyayi and Hamman, 2015).

Statistical analysis

The general linear model (GLM) of SPSS statistical package (version 20) was used for the statistical analysis of results. All the result obtained for the statistical analysis was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine difference within the samples and Duncan multiple range test (Duncan, 1955) was used to determine the difference within the variation at 95% confidence level (Duncan $p > 0.05$). Pearson correlation analysis was also used to determine relationship between different variables investigated.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows results for proximate composition of the Murchi and Kampala varieties of groundnut. Munchi contained 2.53%, 6.72%, 1.94%, 33.94%, 12.80% and 42.37% of moisture, carbohydrate, ash, protein, fibre and lipid, respectively while Kampala contained 5.51%, 2.77%, 1.79%, 24.68%, 16.75%, and 48.80% of moisture, carbohydrate, ash, protein, fibre, and lipid, respectively. Table 2 shows the results for analysis of mineral elements (Ca, Pb, Cd, Fe and P) which revealed

that Kampala has 15.84 Mg/Kg of Ca, 1.79 Mg/Kg of Iron while Munchi contained 19.31 Mg/Kg of Ca, 1.43 Mg/Kg of Iron. Lead, Cadmium and Phosphorus were absent in both variety. Table 3 shows the results for anti-nutrients analysis. The two groundnut variety contained high amounts of Phytate (1480 Mg/100 g for Kampala, 1750 Mg/100 g for Munchi) followed by Oxalate (127.11 Mg/100 g for Kampala, 113.06 Mg/100 g for munchi) and then Cynogenic Glycosides (2.26 Mg/100 g for Kampala and 1.73 Mg/100 g for Munchi). Table 4 shows the results for the amount of antioxidants vitamins A and E present in the 2 groundnut varieties. Vitamin E was absent in both samples but vitamin A was present (6.18 Mg/100 g for Kampala and 7.34 Mg/100 g for Munchi).

DISCUSSION

Proximate analysis stands for a method which determines the values of the macronutrient in food samples. It is of key commercial concern as food manufacturing companies need to ensure that their products meet the appropriate laws and legal declaration requirements as well as the safety aspects of the end products when released to the consumer. In this research carbohydrate, protein, lipid, ash, moisture content and fibre were analyzed for both samples. Moisture content detected in both samples predisposed them to bacterial and fungal attack as a result for the value of moisture not being too high, it can also be stored for a long period of storage time. The low level of carbohydrate in the samples suggested that the groundnut varieties are not good source of carbohydrate. The presence of high protein in the samples (33.94% for Murchi and 24.68% for Kampala) suggested that both samples are good sources of protein. Dietary proteins are needed for the synthesis of new cell wall, repair of worn out tissues, hormones, enzymes, anti-bodies and other substances required for healthy functioning and development of the body and its protection and also for treatment of protein-energy malnutrition (Omoruyi *et al.*, 1994). Lipids which provides strong energy helps in the transport of fat soluble vitamins such as vitamin A, D, E and K and also contribute substantially to the energy value of foods as well as provide essential fatty acids for optimal neurological, immunological and functional development in children (Guthrie, 1989) was present in considerably high amounts in both samples (42.37% for Murchi and 48.80% for Kampala). The ash content analyzed was found to be 1.94% for Murchi and 1.79% for Kampala. Ash content which is the residue remaining after the original matter has been burnt away indicates the presence of minerals in both samples. The samples also contain crude fibre (Kampala (16.75%), Murchi (12.80%). Crude fibre in relation to diet is adequate exerting a major influence on the metabolism of the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and its deficiency is linked to appendicitis, diverticular

Table 1. Proximate composition of the Kampala and Murchi groundnut varieties.

Samples	Moisture content (%)	Carbohydrate (%)	Ash (%)	Crude protein (%)	Crude Fiber (%)	Lipid (%)
Murchi	2.53±0.18 ^b	6.72±0.23 ^b	1.94±0.21 ^a	33.94±1.23 ^b	12.80±0.64 ^b	42.37±0.03 ^b
Kampala	5.51±0.32 ^a	2.77±0.18 ^a	1.79±0.21 ^a	24.68±0.23 ^a	16.75±0.38 ^a	48.80±0.03 ^a

Data expressed as mean ± SEM (N=3); values with different superscript down the column are significantly different from each other at P<0.05.

Table 2. Analysis of mineral elements for the Kampala and Murchi groundnut varieties.

Samples	Ca (Mg/Kg)	Pb (Mg/Kg)	Cd (Mg/Kg)	Fe (Mg/Kg)	P (Mg/Kg)
Kampala	15.84 ± 1.23 ^a	ND	ND	1.79 ± 0.18 ^a	ND
Murchi	19.31± 1.32 ^a	ND	ND	1.43 ± 0.24 ^a	ND

Data expressed as mean ± SEM (N=3); values with different superscript down the column are significantly different from each other at P<0.05.

KEY: ND = Not detected.

Table 3. Anti-nutritional composition of the Kampala and Murchi groundnut varieties.

Samples	Oxalate (Mg/100 g)	Phytate (Mg/100 g)	Cyanogenic Glycoside (Mg/100 g)
Kampala	127.11 ± 2.52 ^a	1480.00 ± 47.92 ^a	2.26 ± 0.10 ^a
Murchi	113.06 ± 1.58 ^b	1750.00 ± 35.79 ^b	1.73 ± 0.17 ^b

Data expressed as mean ± SEM (N=3); values with different superscript down the column are significantly different from each other at P<0.05.

Table 4. Analysis of anti – oxidant vitamins A and E.

Samples	Vitamin A (Mg/100 g)	Vitamin E (Mg/100 g)
Kampala	6.18 ± 0.26 ^a	0.00
Murchi	7.34 ± 0.39 ^a	0.00

Data expressed as mean ± SEM (N=3); values with different superscript down the column are significantly different from each other at P<0.05.

diseases and hemorrhoids (Gibney, 1989).

Mineral elements were analyzed, Calcium was observed as the most abundant mineral element in both samples. Lead, Cadmium and Phosphorous was not detected in all the groundnut varieties used for this research. Calcium is one of the most important minerals for human body; it helps to form and maintains healthy teeth and bones. It also plays a critical role as a messenger in cell signaling pathways throughout the body is necessary for normal cell function, blood coagulation and muscle contractions and relaxation. Deficiency results in osteopenia and osteoporosis, fainting, muscle cramps, heart failure, fatigue, coarse hair etc. (Weaver *et al.*, 2012). Trace amount of Iron was detected in all samples, Murchi (1.43Mg/Kg) and Kampala (1.79 Mg/Kg). Iron is required for the normal functioning of the body and has legumes as one of its source.

The anti-nutrient content investigated in this research as presented in (Table 3) shows that both samples has high levels of phytate and oxalate then traces of Cyanogenic Glycoside. Phytate in foods are known to bind with essential minerals (like Ca, Fe, Mg, and Zn) in

the digestive tract. Oxalate binds with calcium to form calcium oxalate crystals which are deposited as urinary calcium (stones) that are associated with blockage of renal tubules (Blood and Radostits, 1989). Glycoside occurs mostly in plants and serves as an important medicinal substance. It has a carbohydrate and non-carbohydrate residue in the same molecule. Proper food processing such as soaking, sprouting, fermentation and heating would reduce anti-nutrients.

Table 4 shows the analysis of anti-oxidant vitamins (A and E). The findings revealed that vitamin E was absent in both samples while vitamin A was present in both samples. Vitamin A is important in preventing dim light vision. The vitamin A content of the samples was generally low; this maybe because of the length of storage of the groundnut samples.

The findings reveals that the samples are excellent economic source for edible oil production due to the high lipid content found in them especially in the Kampala variety which has the highest value of lipid (48.80%). It is also a good source of protein due to the considerably high amounts of protein found in them. However, the Murchi variety is mostly consumed and used in food more

than the Kampala because of the low level of anti-nutrients found in them which could account for the bitter taste Kampala has when eaten or used in food. The high amounts of anti-nutrients found in the Kampala variety can be reduced by proper processing (cooking, fermentation, sprouting).

Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to provide useful and current information on the chemical composition of the Kampala and Murchi variety of *Arachis hypogaea*, therefore; the study shows the nutritional composition (Proximate, Mineral element and Anti-oxidant Vitamins) and the anti-nutritional factors (Phytate, Oxalate, and Cyanogenic glycoside) of the two groundnut varieties grown in Yola. The findings revealed that the level of anti-nutritional factors (Cyanogenic glycosides and oxalate) which can be toxic was found to be higher in Kampala and it also has high level of moisture content, fibre, lipid and carbohydrate than the Murchi variety. Groundnut seeds can be used for many purposes, depending on the form or state; raw, sun-dry and roasted forms. The considerably high amount of lipid, protein, carbohydrate, fibre, calcium, iron, vitamin A in both of the samples shows that it contributes to important nutrients of man for normal body functioning and also an excellent source of edible oil with significant economic importance due to its use directly in food, animal feeding and confectionery industries.

Recommendations

From the results, the Murchi groundnut variety contained low anti-nutrient composition compared to the Kampala variety; it is recommended that it should be used for consumption after being properly processed. The Kampala with high anti-nutrient factors should be processed more, and its consumption should be limited. The Kampala variety of groundnut should be used in industries such as food industries and chemicals industries where the anti-nutritional content could be detoxified better. This will also make the Murchi variety available for consumption. However, this study revealed the chemical composition of the Kampala and Murchi groundnut varieties grown in Yola, as such there is need for further research on the following:

- (a) Iodine and saponification value of the oil gotten from the Kampala and Murchi groundnut variety.
- (b) Determine amino acid profile and other anti-nutritional factors of the Kampala and Murchi groundnut variety to ascertain the factors that may be responsible for availability and bi-availability of nutrients.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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